

The Flory–Huggins Isotherm and Water Contaminant Adsorption: Debunking Some Modeling Fallacies

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Abstract

The Flory–Huggins (FH) isotherm first appeared in the literature of water contaminant adsorption in the mid-2000s. It has come into the limelight and received considerable attention in recent years, in large part due to regular coverage in review articles. Here, we point out that a linear form of the FH isotherm is incompatible with the original nonlinear version. We show conclusively that the original FH isotherm was destroyed beyond recognition by the linearization method. As a result, the linearized FH isotherm suffers from the following serious defects: (1) Its parameter estimates are incorrect and nonsensical. (2) It is not possible to plot standard isotherm curves in the form of adsorbed phase concentration versus liquid phase concentration. These anomalies, or “red flags,” that arise in the use of the linearized FH isotherm in data correlation are reported for the first time. To avoid publishing meaningless research, it is advisable to use the original form of the FH isotherm in data fitting. To go beyond routine application (e.g., simple data correlation and thermodynamic calculation), this work describes a novel application that uses the FH isotherm to evaluate the energy distribution of heterogeneous adsorbents.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Flory–Huggins (FH) isotherm has been used since the 1960s to describe interfacial processes in studies of electrochemical adsorption and surfactant/polymer adsorption. A version of the FH isotherm gained the attention of chemical engineers in the mid-1980s, who used it to interpret gas adsorption isotherms. Its application in the area of water contaminant adsorption is a relatively recent development. Since the mid-2000s, many studies have reported the modeling of water contaminant adsorption by means of the FH isotherm. Table 1 presents a selection of such studies published across a broad spectrum of scholarly journals.^{1–22} As can be seen in Table 1, the experimental isotherms of numerous water contaminants, ranging from

toxic metals to organic compounds, have been described by the FH isotherm. The inclusion of the FH isotherm in several reviews has no doubt promoted its use in this field of research.^{23–27}

Table 1. Examples of Water Contaminant Adsorption Data Modeled by the FH Isotherm

year of publication	adsorption system	ref
2022	toxic metals/biosorbent	Maity et al. ¹
	dyes/hydrogel	Sharma et al. ²
	dye/metal-organic framework	Mogale et al. ³
	phenol/biochar	Jain et al. ⁴
	phenol/biochar	Emenike et al. ⁵
	dye/boron carbide	Ugraskan et al. ⁶
	Cd(II)/nanocomposite	Li et al. ⁷
	toxic metals/graphene oxide	Abu Elgoud et al. ⁸
	antibiotic & dye/nanocomposite	Motamedi et al. ⁹
2021	drug/activated carbon	Milenković et al. ¹⁰
	oil/nanosorbent	Akpomie and Conradie ¹¹
	toxic metals/biosorbent	Maity et al. ¹²
	Ni(II)/activated carbon	Mathangi et al. ¹³
	Cr(VI)/tea waste	Kabir et al. ¹⁴
	Cu(II)/nanosorbent	Dada et al. ¹⁵
	radionuclides/TiO ₂	Ei-Shazly et al. ¹⁶
2020	dye/clay	Shikuku and Mishra ¹⁷
	toxic metals/hydrogel	Sharma et al. ¹⁸
	dye/lignocellulosic waste	Nayak and Pal ¹⁹
	toxic metals/biosorbent	Guechi and Benabdesselam ²⁰
	Mn(VII)/sediment	Mahmoud et al. ²¹
	Cr(VI)/nanocomposite	Khalil et al. ²²

It seems obvious to state that the mathematical form of an isotherm model selected to describe adsorption must be consistent with its original form. Modifications made to the model must not violate generally accepted physical and chemical principles. Judging from recent publications in the literature of water contaminant adsorption, this seems not to be the case concerning the FH isotherm.

In this contribution, we set out to prove that the mathematical form of the FH isotherm as used in water contaminant adsorption research is fallacious because it has been inappropriately linearized. This erroneous form of the FH isotherm can be found in all the articles listed in Table 1 as well as the reviews cited above.^{1–27} Furthermore, we draw attention

to another fallacy concerning the use of faulty equilibrium constants derived from the linearized FH isotherm to calculate the Gibbs free energy change.

Apart from data correlation, a routine application of the FH isotherm involves thermodynamic calculation. In this work, we present a novel application that uses the FH isotherm to evaluate the energy distribution of heterogeneous adsorbents. Unnecessary though this will be for researchers familiar with the intricacies of adsorption isotherm modeling, an overview of the FH isotherm is provided here, which serves as a good starting point for interested readers to explore further.

2. THEORY

The FH isotherm for liquid phase adsorption is written as eq 1, where b is an equilibrium constant, c is the equilibrium liquid phase concentration, $\theta = q/q_m$ is the fractional amount adsorbed, q is the adsorbed phase concentration, q_m is the saturation capacity, k is a parameter associated with interactions between adsorbed molecules, and n is a constant whose physical meaning depends on the theoretical model used to derive eq 1. When $n = 1$, eq 1 transforms itself into the Frumkin–Fowler–Guggenheim isotherm; when $n = 1$ and $k = 0$, eq 1 reverts to the familiar Langmuir isotherm.

$$bc = \frac{\theta}{(1-\theta)^n} \exp(-k\theta) \quad (1)$$

Because a polymer-monomer solution theory due independently to Flory²⁸ and Huggins²⁹ was used by some researchers to derive eq 1, the isotherm equation was credited to Flory and Huggins, although they played no role in its derivation. Flory, the 1974 Nobel laureate in chemistry, acknowledged that the FH solution theory should bear the two names in reverse order because Huggins's publication preceded his own by a month or two.³⁰

The FH isotherm is the result of deductions based on various theoretical models. Henry³¹ derived eq 1 without the exponential term ($k = 0$) from kinetic theory. Honig and Mueller³² modified the FH theory to obtain eq 1 for monolayer gas adsorption. Nitta et al.³³ developed eq 1 for gas adsorption using statistical thermodynamic arguments and assuming localized monolayer adsorption in which the adsorbed molecule occupies a certain number of active sites. Bashiri and Eris^{34,35} used arguments from classical and statistical thermodynamics to derive eq 1 for gas adsorption by considering different chemisorption geometries of an adsorbate and ignoring interactions between adsorbed molecules ($k = 0$). Their studies showed that the exponent n is the ratio of the number of occupied sites to the number of adsorbed molecules. In the literature of electrochemical adsorption, eq 1 is attributed to the thermodynamic treatment of Zhukovitskii.^{36,37} Finally, eq 1 could be derived from a two-dimensional solution theory formulated to describe protein/surfactant adsorption at water-fluid interfaces.^{38,39} It should be mentioned that the original FH solution theory has been successfully used to interpret adsorption equilibria for the uptake of organic contaminants by natural geosorbents.⁴⁰

Given the diversity of its theoretical roots, it is not surprising to see that different forms of the FH isotherm exist. For example, the multisite occupancy model proposed by Nitta et al.³³ is written as eq 2, where b_1 is an equilibrium constant, n , in this case, denotes the number of sites occupied by one adsorbed molecule, u is the adsorbate-adsorbate interaction parameter, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T is the temperature. The multisite occupancy model of Nitta et al. is also known as the multisite Langmuir model.⁴¹⁻⁴³ It is evident that eq 1 is analogous to eq 2 since $b = nb_1$ and $k = nu/k_B T$.

$$b_1 c = \frac{\theta}{n(1-\theta)^n} \exp\left(-\frac{nu}{k_B T} \theta\right) \quad (2)$$

As an aside, we mention three related isotherm models that may be of interest to some readers. The first isotherm model, eq 3, is an extended form of eq 1 devised for gas adsorption, where P is the gas pressure and s is a parameter associated with the loss of symmetry or chemical dissociation of adsorbed molecules.⁴⁴ When there is no loss of symmetry or chemical dissociation ($s = 1$), eq 3 reduces to the FH isotherm.

$$bP = \frac{\theta^s}{(1-\theta)^n} \exp(-k\theta) \quad (3)$$

The second isotherm model has a direct link to the FH theory. By introducing the FH activity coefficient into the vacancy solution model, Cochran et al.⁴⁵ derived eq 4 for gas adsorption, where N^∞ , b_v , and α_v are model parameters. Equation 4 is referred to as the FH form of the vacancy solution model (FH-VSM). A thermodynamically consistent FH-VSM has been derived by Bhatia and Ding,⁴⁶ which is similar to eq 2.

$$b_v P = N^\infty \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_v^2 \theta}{1+\alpha_v \theta}\right) \quad (4)$$

The third isotherm model is based on the multisite occupancy concept developed for the adsorption of linear adsorbates on homogeneous surfaces. Romá et al.⁴⁷ presented a comparative evaluation of this model (eq 5) and eq 1 without the adsorbate-adsorbate interaction term.

$$bP = \frac{\theta}{(1-\theta)^n} \left[1 - \frac{(n-1)}{n} \theta\right]^{n-1} \quad (5)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Fallacy 1. To correlate hyperbolic or type I isotherm data, a simpler form of the FH isotherm (eq 1) is preferred. By assuming that the adsorbed molecules are noninteracting ($k = 0$), eq 1 reduces to eq 6. However, eq 6 is rarely used to fit water contaminant adsorption data. In keeping with the long-standing tradition of model linearization, eq 6 has been

rearranged to take the form given by eq 7, implying that a plot of its left-hand side member against $\ln(1 - \theta)$ should yield a straight line.

$$bc = \frac{\theta}{(1 - \theta)^n} \quad (6)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{\theta}{c}\right) = \ln(b) + n \ln(1 - \theta) \quad (7)$$

Oddly, a modified form of eq 7, given here by eq 8, is the most widely used FH isotherm in this field of research.⁴⁸ The only difference between eqs 7 and 8 is that the c -term in the former has been replaced by c_0 , which is the initial solute concentration in the liquid phase.

$$\ln\left(\frac{\theta}{c_0}\right) = \ln(b) + n \ln(1 - \theta) \quad (8)$$

The direct substitution of c with c_0 implies that c is equivalent to c_0 . This mathematical manipulation motivates the following question: What is the origin of the equality $c = c_0$? No answer to this question could be found in the literature of water contaminant adsorption. There is one well-known link between c and c_0 : the mass balance equation for a batch adsorber, as given by eq 9, where α is the adsorbent dosage (mass of adsorbent/volume of solution) and q_0 is the initial solute concentration in the adsorbed phase. In the usual case of a pristine adsorbent, q_0 is zero. According to eq 9, $c = c_0$ is valid when $\alpha = 0$ or $q = 0$. However, these conditions imply that no adsorbent is present in the batch adsorber or that there is zero adsorption! Replacing the c -term in eq 7 with c_0 makes no sense. Incredibly, the nonsensical eq 8 is widely used to fit isotherm data and is regularly promoted in review articles.

$$c = c_0 - \alpha(q - q_0) \quad (9)$$

3.2. Fallacy 2. Here, we dissect another specious modification of the linearized FH isotherm. To perform a linear plot on eq 8, the value of θ must be known. As previously stated, θ is defined as q/q_m . The variable q is a known quantity; it can be calculated from the mass balance equation given by eq 9 if adsorption experiments are conducted in batch contactors.

By contrast, the q_m -term is usually treated as an unknown parameter. This implies that θ is an unknown quantity. To avoid this inconvenience, many researchers have used eq 10 to calculate the θ -term in eq 8.⁴⁸

$$\theta = 1 - \frac{c}{c_0} \quad (10)$$

Like the equality $c = c_0$ discussed above, the validity of eq 10 has never been proven. We suspect that it is a modification of the mass balance equation for batch adsorption, i.e., eq 9, which can be written as eq 11, where $\beta = c_0/(\alpha q_m)$. If $\beta = 1$, it is obvious that eq 11 reduces to eq 10. However, it is difficult, if not impossible, to make β equal to unity for two reasons. First, because either the initial solute concentration c_0 or the adsorbent dosage α in typical batch experiments is varied to generate a series of equilibrium data, β cannot be a fixed quantity. Second, the q_m -term in β remains an unknown parameter. As a result, $\beta = 1$ cannot be realized in practice. Accordingly, eq 10 is fallacious if it is indeed a modification of the mass balance equation. Note that if we apply the equality $c = c_0$ to eq 10, we obtain $\theta = 0$, suggesting that there is zero adsorption. Apparently, application of the equality $c = c_0$ is confined to eq 7; it cannot be used elsewhere.

$$\theta = \frac{1}{\alpha q_m} \left(1 - \frac{c}{c_0} \right) = \beta \left(1 - \frac{c}{c_0} \right) \quad (11)$$

Historically, eqs 8 and 10 seem to originate from a 2005 paper published by Horsfall and Spiff,⁴⁹ who provided the two equations without any derivation or reference citation. It is unfortunate that eqs 8 and 10 have until now not been subjected to a critical analysis. In 2009, Liu⁴⁸ expressed reservations about the appropriateness of these two equations but did not go far enough to assert that they were illogical.

3.3. Consequences of Fallacies 1 and 2. The linearized FH isotherm (eq 8) has been used to interpret numerous experimental isotherms of water contaminants, some of which are

listed in Table 1. To gauge the implications of using eq 8 in data correlation, we compare the modeling results obtained from eqs 6 and 8. The former is a proper form of the FH isotherm.

Combining eqs 8 and 10 yields eq 12, which will be used to fit a data set taken from the work of Vijayaraghavan et al.⁵⁰ These authors were most likely the first to apply eq 12, proposed by Horsfall and Spiff,⁴⁹ to adsorption data. Many subsequent studies employing eq 12 in data correlation as well as several reviews promoting the FH isotherm have cited the work of Vijayaraghavan et al.⁵⁰ Evidently, this paper has played an important role in the propagation of eq 12 in water contaminant adsorption research. Note that if we apply the equality $c = c_0$ to eq 12, the left-hand side member becomes undefined. It seems that this is not something we should worry about because the equality $c = c_0$ can only be used once to derive eq 8.

$$\ln\left(\frac{c_0 - c}{c_0^2}\right) = \ln(b) + n \ln\left(\frac{c}{c_0}\right) \quad (12)$$

Figure 1. (A) Adsorption isotherm for Ni(II) adsorption on a seaweed biomass.⁵⁰ (B) Linear fit of the FH isotherm (eq 12) to the Ni(II) adsorption data plotted in (A).

Figure 1A depicts the chosen isotherm for Ni(II) adsorption on a seaweed biomass at pH 4. In the original study, the linear fit of eq 12 to the Ni(II) isotherm produced $b = 289.7$ and $n = 3.67$.⁵⁰ Figure 1B presents our linear regression result. Values of c_0 , required by eq 12, were not given in the original study. Here, they were calculated from the mass balance equation (eq

9) using the q versus c data points in Figure 1A and the given adsorbent dosage (a) of 2 g L^{-1} . As seen in Figure 1B, the linear fit is excellent, returning $R^2 = 0.990$, $b = 2.98 \times 10^{-5} \text{ L mg}^{-1}$, and $n = -10.17$.

Our parameter estimates differ greatly from the reported ones. A comparison of the b values is meaningless since the original study did not report any units for b , which should be expressed in units of the reciprocal of the liquid phase concentration. Our primary concern is the sign of n . Given that the linear plot in Figure 1B has a negative slope, the arithmetic value of n in eq 12 should also be negative. The sign of our estimate ($n = -10.17$) seems correct, as supported by several studies listed in Table 1, which have also reported negative estimates for n . The positive value reported in the original study⁵⁰ ($n = 3.67$) is thus suspect. Unfortunately, the corresponding linear regression plot was not shown in the original study,⁵⁰ making it difficult to verify the sign of the reported n . Nonetheless, positive estimates for n have also been reported by some of the studies listed in Table 1.

To resolve the conundrum, eq 12 was applied to two new data sets. The estimate for n reported in the work of Mogale et al.³ was a positive value ($n = 11.38$), obtained by a linear fit of eq 12 to the experimental isotherm for celestine blue dye adsorption by a metal-organic framework. In another study, Varala et al.⁵¹ also reported a positive estimate ($n = 3.55$) after fitting eq 12 to the experimental isotherm for Zr(IV) adsorption by a biosorbent. However, the linear regression plots shown in these two studies^{3,51} displayed negative slopes, contradicting the positive estimates for n .

Here, eq 12 was fitted to the dye and Zr(IV) isotherms, as shown in Figure 2. The slopes of the two linear plots in Figure 2 give $n = -11.52$ for the dye data and $n = -3.8$ for the Zr(IV) data. Our estimates are similar in magnitude to the respective reported values, but with a negative sign. It is clear that Mogale et al.³ and Varala et al.⁵¹ made an elementary mistake in

reporting the sign of n . This analysis casts doubt on the positive values of n reported in other studies, including the work of Vijayaraghavan et al.⁵⁰ analyzed above.

Figure 2. (A) Linear fit of the FH isotherm (eq 12) to celestine blue dye adsorption.³ (B) Linear fit of the FH isotherm (eq 12) to Zr(IV) adsorption data.⁵¹

Returning to our objective of comparing eqs 6 and 8 (or 12), to ensure a meaningful comparison, it is imperative that the data fitting results obtained from eq 12 are verifiable. We found such a set of results in one of the reports listed in Table 1. In a recent study, Nayak and Pal¹⁹ used 35 isotherm models, including the FH isotherm, to interpret the adsorption of acridine orange dye by an agricultural waste material at three different temperatures. Figure 3A presents the dye isotherm measured at 30 °C. In the original study, eq 12 was fitted to the dye adsorption data by linear regression to yield $b = 1.644 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ and $n = -1.64$.

In this work, eq 12 was fitted to the dye adsorption data by linear regression using the c_0 values given in the original study and the c values extracted from Figure 3A. The linear fit is satisfactory ($R^2 = 0.977$; Figure 3B), returning $b = 1.58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ and $n = -1.67$. Our parameter estimates agree well with the findings of the original study. Next, we turn to comparing these verified parameter estimates to those produced by eq 6.

Figure 3. (A) Adsorption isotherm for acridine orange dye adsorption on an agricultural waste.¹⁹ (B) Linear fit of the FH isotherm (eq 12) to the dye adsorption data plotted in (A).

Equation 6, rearranged as eq 13, has three unknown parameters: q_m , b , and n . Because eq 13 is implicit in q , conventional least-squares fitting algorithms require modification before they can be used to minimize the sum of the squares of the differences between experimental q and q calculated from eq 13. In this work, a nonlinear least-squares method known as orthogonal distance regression (OriginPro 2019b),^{52,53} which minimizes the residual errors in both c and q , was used to fit eq 13 to the measured dye isotherm depicted in Figure 3A. Note that eq 13 can be rearranged to yield an expression explicit in c , which allows the use of conventional least-squares algorithms to minimize the residual errors in c (see the Supporting Information for details).

$$q = q_m^{(1-n)} (q_m - q)^n bc \quad (13)$$

Figure 4 shows the nonlinear fit of eq 13, while Table 2 compares the resulting parameter estimates to those obtained by eq 12. It is immediately obvious that the results obtained by eq 13 are vastly different from those produced by eq 12. The b value obtained by eq 13 is greater than that produced by eq 12 by a factor of more than 110!

Figure 4. Nonlinear fit of the FH isotherm (eq 13) to acridine orange dye adsorption data measured at 30 °C.¹⁹

Table 2. Parameter Estimates Obtained by Fits of Eqs 12 and 13 to Acridine Orange Dye Adsorption Data Measured at 30 °C¹⁹

parameter	eq 12	eq 13
b (L mg ⁻¹)	1.58×10^{-4}	0.018
n	-1.67	1.15
q_m (mg g ⁻¹)	-	285.02
R^2	0.977	0.998

Furthermore, the value of n obtained by eq 13 is positive, whereas the one produced by eq 12 is negative. So, we may ask: Does a negative n make sense? As we have noted in section 2, several theoretical models have been used to derive the FH isotherm. For example, in the multisite occupancy model proposed by Nitta et al.,³³ n is used to denote the number of adsorbent sites occupied by one adsorbed molecule. According to a lattice model of electrochemical adsorption,^{36,37} n is the number of solvent molecules displaced by an adsorbate molecule. Unlike the interaction parameter k in eq 1 (positive for attraction; negative for repulsion), n , with its restrictive conceptual connotations, must attain positive values. Even if

n is treated as an empirical parameter and allowed to roam freely in data fitting, a negative value should raise a red flag about the soundness of eq 12.

Figure 5. (A) Variation of q_m calculated from eq 14 with c . (B) Variation of q_m calculated from eq 14 with q . Values of c and q were taken from Figure 4.

No comparison of q_m can be made because q_m is not a fitting parameter in eq 12. But it seems that q_m can be calculated from eq 10, which is rewritten as eq 14. This equation allows us to calculate q_m since c , c_0 , and q are known experimental quantities. Using the data for the dye isotherm depicted in Figure 4, q_m values calculated from eq 14 are plotted as a function of c or q in Figure 5. What should be apparent to the reader from looking at Figure 5 is that the variation of q_m with c or q is a blatant violation of the definition of q_m . This absurd property of eq 14 has never been pointed out before; q_m is in essence a forgotten parameter. To summarize, while the linearized FH isotherm represented by eq 12 can fit data well, its parameter estimates are not only incorrect but also illogical.

$$q_m = \frac{qc_0}{c_0 - c} \quad (14)$$

Researchers may not recognize another incongruity in eq 8 or 12 if they are only interested in obtaining b and n from adsorption data by linear regression. This absurdity becomes immediately apparent if one tries to plot a q versus c isotherm curve by plugging the

linear regression-generated parameter estimates into eq 8 or 12. Equation 8, rewritten as eq 15, is devoid of the liquid phase concentration c . Likewise, eq 12, reproduced below as eq 16, lacks the adsorbed phase concentration q . Consequently, neither equation is able to make q versus c predictions even if all the model parameters are known. This is the reason why no predicted curves of q versus c are shown in Figures 1A and 3A.

$$\ln\left(\frac{q}{q_m c_0}\right) = \ln(b) + n \ln\left(1 - \frac{q}{q_m}\right) \quad (15)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{c_0 - c}{c_0^2}\right) = \ln(b) + n \ln\left(\frac{c}{c_0}\right) \quad (16)$$

The need for plotting q versus c isotherm curves has been ignored by most users of the linearized FH isotherm, seduced by its ability to provide attractive R^2 scores for its linear fits. We stress that an isotherm model should be judged on its ability to predict the untransformed data in the form of q versus c . Most linearized isotherm models are evaluated and compared based on their ability to fit different sets of transformed data by linear regression. This biased method of model comparison has recently been criticized by Debord et al.⁵⁴

Table 3 provides a summary of the various versions of the FH isotherm discussed in this work.

Table 3. Different Versions of the FH Isotherm

version	equation	mathematical form	comment
complete FH	1	$bc = \frac{\theta}{(1-\theta)^n} \exp(-k\theta)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 fitting parameters • fits sigmoid (type V) isotherms
simplified FH	13	$q = q_m^{(1-n)} (q_m - q)^n bc$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 fitting parameters • fits hyperbolic (type I) isotherms • implicit in q • data fitting by nonstandard regression methods
simplified FH	S2	$c = \frac{q}{bq_m^{(1-n)} (q_m - q)^n}$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 fitting parameters • fits hyperbolic (type I) isotherms • explicit in c • data fitting by standard regression methods (e.g., Excel Solver)
linearized FH	12	$\ln\left(\frac{c_0 - c}{c_0^2}\right) = \ln(b) + n \ln\left(\frac{c}{c_0}\right)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 fitting parameters • data fitting by linear regression • provides good linear fits but yields erroneous and nonsensical parameters • cannot plot q versus c isotherm curves • discussed briefly by Liu⁴⁸

3.4. Fitting an Elephant. With three free parameters, it is not surprising that the nonlinear FH isotherm (eq 13) can give a good fit to the experimental data depicted in Figure 4. However, many experimental hyperbolic curves, such as the one depicted in Figure 4, are well represented by the two-parameter equation of Langmuir or Freundlich. To investigate whether the FH isotherm fit in Figure 4 is a case of overfitting, the two-parameter Langmuir isotherm was applied to the experimental data by means of nonlinear regression. As noted earlier, when $n = 1$, the FH isotherm (eq 13) reverts to the Langmuir isotherm. Figure 6 shows that the Langmuir isotherm fit, calculated using $b = 0.017 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ and $q_m = 273.4 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$, is practically identical to the FH isotherm fit plotted in Figure 4. Indeed, both model fits share the

same R^2 score of 0.998. From the curve-fitting perspective, there is no advantage to using the FH isotherm in correlating the Figure 4 data because the parameter n is superfluous (n is not significantly bigger than unity). In this case, the exponent n can be set equal to unity without sacrificing accuracy.

Figure 6. Nonlinear fit of the Langmuir isotherm to acridine orange dye adsorption data measured at 30 °C.¹⁹

Nevertheless, in this field of research, isotherm models with multiple free parameters are frequently used to correlate simple, well-behaved hyperbolic curves. For example, in the original study,¹⁹ several isotherm models with as many as four or five free parameters were used to fit the simple hyperbolic curve depicted in Figure 4. The phenomenon of frivolous data fitting drew a famous quip from the great polymath John von Neumann, who said: “With four parameters I can fit an elephant and with five I can make him wiggle his trunk.”⁵⁵ Indeed, it is possible to construct von Neumann’s elephant with four complex parameters (and with a fifth to include trunk-wiggling).⁵⁶ However, von Neumann’s assertion was recently proven to be false; an elephantine shape could be drawn using a one-parameter function.⁵⁷

Of course, we will readily concede that one should use the FH isotherm in data fitting if its parameters can be interpreted in terms of their theoretical connotations. However, that is

not the case with most studies on water contaminant adsorption; the linearized FH isotherm is merely an empirical curve-fitting tool that offers mathematical convenience. Although not investigated here, we mention in passing that the FH isotherm with four free parameters (eq 1) is capable of describing sigmoid or S-shaped adsorption data.

3.5. Fallacy 3. In this section, we discuss another fallacy concerning the use of the equilibrium constant b in the FH isotherm to calculate ΔG (the Gibbs free energy change). As previously stated, Nayak and Pal¹⁹ obtained a value of $1.644 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ for b by fitting eq 12 to the acridine orange dye adsorption data measured at 30 °C. Two more estimates for b were given in the original study,¹⁹ which were obtained by fitting eq 12 to adsorption data measured at 15 and 45 °C. These reported values of b are summarized in Table 4. Nayak and Pal¹⁹ calculated ΔG by plugging the values of b into eq 17, where R is the universal gas constant. The reported ΔG estimates are presented in Table 4. Note that these ΔG estimates were incorrectly given as negative values in the original study.¹⁹

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln(b) \quad (17)$$

Table 4. Comparison of ΔG Values of the Original Study¹⁹ and ΔG° Values of the Present Study

temperature (°C)	study	b (L mg ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	b°	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)
15	original	1.183×10^{-4}	21.65			
	present			0.011	2918.85	-19.11
30	original	1.644×10^{-4}	21.95			
	present			0.018	4776.3	-21.35
45	original	2.679×10^{-4}	21.75			
	present			0.029	7695.15	-23.67

It is unclear why Nayak and Pal¹⁹ calculated ΔG using only the modeling results of the FH isotherm (one out of 35 isotherm models). As we have explained above (see section 3.3), their use of the farcical eq 12 has no real meaning nor utility. Thus, more realistic values for ΔG can be calculated using the correct values of b obtained by eq 13. However, one should not

forget that one can only take the logarithm of a dimensionless parameter! Moreover, to take the logarithm of the “thermodynamic equilibrium constant” (unitless), the concentration unit should be in mol L⁻¹ (not mg L⁻¹ or any other). Although this should be a well-known fact, it is all too often forgotten, as recently discussed by several researchers.^{58–60}

In the specific case of acridine orange dye adsorption, one must convert the FH equilibrium constant b (L mg⁻¹) to the corresponding (dimensionless) thermodynamic equilibrium constant b° for the adsorption process. To do this, one should use eq 18, where the factor 1000 converts g to mg, $M_{dye} = 265.35$ g mol⁻¹ is the acridine orange molar mass, and C° is the standard concentration of acridine orange (1 mol L⁻¹). Then, one can calculate the standard Gibbs free energy change ΔG° according to eq 19.

$$b^\circ = b \left[\text{L mg}^{-1} \right] \times 1000 \left[\text{mg g}^{-1} \right] \times M_{dye} \left[\text{g mol}^{-1} \right] \times C^\circ \left[\text{mol L}^{-1} \right] \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln(b^\circ) \quad (19)$$

Table 4 presents the estimates for b obtained by fitting eq 13 to the three data sets measured at 15, 30, and 45 °C using the method of orthogonal distance regression. The fitting results are shown in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information (Figure 4 shows one of the fits). Plugging the values of b (Table 3), M_{dye} (265.35 g mol⁻¹), and C° (1 mol L⁻¹) into eq 18 gives the estimates for b° , listed in Table 4. The ΔG° values calculated from eq 19 using the b° estimates are also presented in Table 4. Our estimates for ΔG° differ greatly from the estimates for ΔG reported by Nayak and Pal.¹⁹ Most noticeably, the ΔG° estimates are negative while the ΔG estimates are positive. The calculation of ΔG in the original study is marred by two fallacies: (1) The estimates for b were obtained from the farcical eq 12. (2) The ΔG values were calculated from the defective eq 17 using the estimates for b expressed in units of L mg⁻¹.

3.6. Reformulation of the FH Isotherm. The modeling results of the FH isotherm are commonly used to calculate thermodynamic quantities, such as the Gibbs free energy change

discussed in section 3.5. Here, we describe a novel application that uses the FH isotherm to evaluate the energy distribution of an heterogeneous adsorbent. For such applications, it is more convenient to use isotherm models explicit in q . The FH isotherm is implicit in q but can be reformulated into an explicit version based on one of the previously known isotherms. Using simulations, we noticed that the FH isotherm (eq 6) was best approximated by a variant of the Langmuir–Elovich isotherm, given here by eq 20, which was recently introduced by Debord et al.⁵⁴ In eq 20, A , B , and η are fitting parameters, q_m and b are the original parameters of the FH isotherm, and W is the Lambert W function, such that if $y = W(x)$, then $x = y \exp(y)$. Note that eq 20 is explicit in q .

$$q = q_m \frac{A \cdot W(\eta bc)}{1 + B \cdot W(\eta bc)} \quad (20)$$

The reformulation of the loading-implicit FH isotherm in terms of the loading-explicit eq 20 involves determining the empirical relationships between the FH exponent n and the fitting parameters of eq 20 (A , B , and η). In the field of gas phase adsorption, Table 5 shows that $n > 13$ has been reported. In liquid phase adsorption research, Table 6 shows that n was generally found to be less than 3. Accordingly, we have selected the following range for n : $1.1 \leq n \leq 5$. Figure S3 of the Supporting Information shows the approximation of several simulated curves of the FH isotherm by eq 20, while Figure S4 plots the empirical relationships between the parameters of eq 20 (A , B , and η) and n . From Figure S4, the following relationships can be derived:

$$\frac{1}{A} = 1.0455n - 1.0233 \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{1}{B} = 1.6797n - 1.8678 \quad (22)$$

$$\eta = 1.0226n - 1.0123 \quad (23)$$

Other isotherm models may be used to approximate the FH isotherm. For example, the Sips isotherm also gave a good approximation but with higher residual values (see the Supporting Information for details).

Table 5. Reported Values of n for Gas Phase Adsorption

adsorbent	adsorbate	n	ref
carbon molecular sieve	CH ₄	6.329	Yang et al. ⁴³
	N ₂	6.271	
zeolite 13X	CH ₄	8.136	Cavenati et al. ⁶¹
	CO ₂	13.120	
	N ₂	7.917	
activated carbon	CH ₄	2.57	Grande et al. ⁶²
	CO ₂	1.69	
NaY zeolite	CO ₂	1.848	Shirani and Eic ⁶³
	CO	1.945	
	C ₂ H ₄	2.707	
4A zeolite	C ₃ H ₆	2.612	Kuah et al. ⁶⁴
	C ₃ H ₈	2.189	
carbon molecular sieve	CH ₄	2.77	Canevesi et al. ⁶⁵
	CO ₂	1.84	
polymeric material	CO ₂	1.04; 1.44; 1.49	Ansari et al. ⁶⁶

Table 6. Reported Values of n for Liquid Phase Adsorption

adsorbent	adsorbate	n	ref
activated carbon	salicylic acid	1.573	Otero et al. ⁶⁷
polymeric resin		1.711	
natural zeolite	crystal violet	1.22	Sarabadan et al. ⁶⁸
activated carbon		2.67	
activated carbon	phenol	1.77	Shukla et al. ⁶⁹
	chlorophenol	1.67	
	dichlorophenol	1.65	
	trichlorophenol	1.21	
attapulgit	copper	1	El Bardiji et al. ⁷⁰
modified clay	crystal violet	1.23; 1.36; 1.50	Sarabadan et al. ⁷¹

3.7. Evaluation of Energy Distribution. As a case study, we will use the data fitting results reported by Sarabadan et al.⁶⁸ to evaluate the energy distribution of an heterogeneous adsorbent. In the work of Sarabadan et al.,⁶⁸ an activated carbon adsorbent was used to remove the dye crystal violet from aqueous solution. Activated carbons are well known for their strong

heterogeneous surfaces.⁷² The FH isotherm equation used by Sarabadan et al.⁶⁸ is given by eq 24, where K_{FH} is an equilibrium constant. The reported values for the three FH parameters in eq 24 were $q_m = 91.48 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$, $K_{FH} = 34.14 \text{ (mg L}^{-1}\text{)(mg g}^{-1}\text{)}^{n-1}$, and $n = 2.67$. Since n is markedly greater than unity, the Langmuir isotherm is not expected to give a good fit, and the use of the FH isotherm in this case seems justified.

$$\frac{c}{K_{FH}} = \frac{q}{(q_m - q)^n} \quad (24)$$

By comparing eq 24 with our FH formulation given by eq 13, we obtain eq 25, which gives $b = (91.48)^{1.67}/34.14 = 55.23 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$. With the molar mass of $407.99 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ for crystal violet and the calculated b value, the nondimensional FH binding constant calculated from eq 18 is $b^\circ = 55.23 \times 1000 \times 407.99 \times 1 = 2.253 \times 10^7$. Then, the standard adsorption free energy calculated from eq 19 is $\Delta G^\circ = -8.314 \times 298 \times \ln(2.253 \times 10^7) = -41.95 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

$$b = \frac{q_m^{n-1}}{K_{FH}} \quad (25)$$

For an heterogeneous adsorbent, the energy E is statistically distributed with a mean value (E_0). The probability density function (p.d.f.) of E is given by eq 26.⁵⁴ The function $f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon)$ in eq 26 is defined by eq 27, where ε is given by eq 28.

$$f_E(E) = \frac{f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon)}{RT} \quad (26)$$

$$f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) = \frac{B \cdot W [\exp(-\varepsilon)]}{\{1 + B \cdot W [\exp(-\varepsilon)]\}^2 \cdot \{1 + W [\exp(-\varepsilon)]\}} \quad (27)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{(E - E_0)}{RT} \quad (28)$$

To plot the p.d.f. against E , knowledge of E_0 and B is needed. For the Langmuir–Elovich reformulation of the FH isotherm, the binding constant is ηb° , so the mean energy E_0

is given by eq 29. When $n = 2.67$, eq 23 yields $\eta = 1.718$. As a result, $E_0 = -43.29 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ is obtained from eq 29. When $n = 2.67$, we obtain $B = 0.382$ from eq 22.

$$E_0 = -RT \ln(\eta b^\circ) = \Delta G^\circ - RT \ln(\eta) \quad (29)$$

With all the parameters known, eq 26 can be used to plot the p.d.f. against E , as shown in Figure 7. The curve has a long tail in the high energy domain (most negative E values). This may suggest that the adsorbate binds to a variable number of sites, the noninteger value of n being a mean value ($n = 2.67$). Given that the FH isotherm is mostly used to calculate simple thermodynamic quantities, the energy distribution analysis presented above represents a novel contribution of this work.

Figure 7. Energy distribution for the adsorption of crystal violet onto an activated carbon adsorbent.⁶⁸

4. Conclusions

Model linearization has long dominated the modeling landscape of water contaminant adsorption research. The Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms are two such models that have been subjected to linearization. Although there are statistical problems, linearization affords a simple way to estimate the two parameters of the Langmuir or Freundlich equation from the

slope and intercept of a straight line. However, ingenious mathematical tricks are needed to linearize isotherm models with more than two parameters. Given that the FH isotherm is a three-parameter expression (q_m , b , and n), there is no simple way of linearizing it. The seemingly nifty tricks used to linearize the FH isotherm turned out to be fallacious.

This study has identified the following contentious issues concerning the parameters of the linearized FH isotherm:

- The fitted value of b was found to differ significantly from the corresponding value obtained by the original FH isotherm. As a consequence, further calculation of the Gibbs free energy change was utterly meaningless.
- The fitted value of n was found to be negative, compromising its physical meaning.
- The calculated value of q_m was found to vary with the liquid or adsorbed phase concentration, violating its theoretical definition.

Adding to the aforementioned anomalies, the linearized FH isotherm cannot be used to plot standard q versus c isotherm curves. It no longer exists as an isotherm model! In essence, the linearized FH isotherm bears little formal resemblance to the original FH isotherm. This means that the modeling results of the linearized FH isotherm reported in all previously published studies have been mostly misleading and meaningless. We take no pleasure in this conclusion, but it is imperative to sound the alarm bell about the danger posed by the farcical linearized FH isotherm. One thing we can say for certain is that the linearized FH isotherm is not the only ludicrous equation in this field of research. Many researchers seem to believe with blind faith that a printed equation is infallible.

Of course, there are no issues with the original three-parameter FH isotherm, which can do a good job of describing hyperbolic or type I isotherm data (the four-parameter version can fit sigmoid or type V isotherm data). However, data fitting with the three-parameter FH isotherm is somewhat tricky because it is implicit in q . Besides data correlation and

thermodynamic calculation, the FH isotherm can be used to evaluate the energy distribution of heterogeneous adsorbents, as shown in this work. For this novel application, the loading-implicit FH isotherm was converted to an explicit form.

Supporting Information

Fits of the Flory–Huggins isotherm to adsorption data of acridine orange. Approximation of the Flory–Huggins isotherm by the Langmuir–Elovich isotherm and the Sips isotherm.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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